

OCEAN ICE News – November 2025

OCEAN ICE is a Horizon Europe project, funded by the European Commission and UKRI. OCEAN ICE stands for Ocean-Cryosphere Exchanges in Antarctica: Impacts on Climate and the Earth System.

OCEAN ICE News is a monthly newsletter updating about the project's progress, results, and other exciting events! Be sure to follow us on LinkedIn to stay informed.

Welcome!

Welcome to November's edition of OCEAN ICE News. We're excited to bring you the latest updates from the OCEAN ICE community.

In this issue, you'll meet our featured researcher of the month and catch up on key activities, such as OCEAN ICE at Polar CORDEX, A recent OCEAN ICE Publication, highlighting September and October's Climate Coffee. We have some upcoming Climate Coffee's that you can register for in November and December. Don't forget to mark your calendars for the upcoming events where OCEAN ICE will be represented.

We hope you enjoy exploring this month's updates, and we look forward to sharing more in December!

Researcher in the Spotlight: Rachele Bordoni

Check out our latest 'Researcher in the Spotlight' feature on Rachele Bordoni, a Project Manager at ETT S.p.A.

Read the feature on Rachele [here](#).

Stay tuned for more features from our Research Team in OCEAN ICE.

Catching up on the Latest OCEAN ICE Activities

OCEAN ICE at Polar CORDEX 2025

Members of the OCEAN ICE WP3 attended the Polar CORDEX meeting at the British Antarctic Survey in Cambridge. The meeting focused on regional climate modelling in the polar regions.

Marte Hofsteenge presented the evaluation of regional climate model simulations from the EU PolarRES project.

Read the full article [here](#).

OCEAN ICE Publication: Freshwater Sources in the Global Ocean Through Salinity- $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ Relationships: A Machine Learning Solution to a Water Mass Problem

Understanding where freshwater in the ocean comes from — and how it moves — is crucial for predicting changes in ocean circulation and climate.

In our new paper, Xabier, Elaine et al. used a machine learning approach to trace freshwater sources from precipitation, ice sheets, rivers, and melting sea ice across the global ocean.

In the Southern Ocean, reduced sea ice formation is making deep waters fresher.

In the Arctic, surface waters are becoming fresher due to increased sea ice melt.

The Northern and Southern Hemispheres have very different freshwater budgets, mainly because sea ice plays contrasting roles in forming deep waters.

These results help us better understand how the ocean's freshwater system is shifting in response to climate change.

The paper shows that some of the deepest water masses in Antarctica are getting fresher, not because ice sheet melt, but rather because there is less sea ice being formed. Similar but different, in Arctic, waters are getting fresher because there is more sea ice melt.

Catch up with the full article [here](#).

 OCEAN:ICE

OCEAN:ICE Paper Published:

Freshwater Sources in the Global Ocean Through Salinity- $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ Relationships: A Machine Learning Solution to a Water Mass Problem

 Funded by the European Union

 UK Research and Innovation

UK Partners are funded by UK Research and Innovation (UKRI) under the UK government's Horizon Europe funding Guarantee.

OCEAN ICE Climate coffee – September

Climate Coffee with Audrey Minière on Estimating ocean warming: Challenges & recommendations for robust assessment

Human-induced emissions have driven the Earth into an energy imbalance, resulting in the accumulation of excess heat within the climate system. Approximately 90% of this surplus energy is absorbed by the global ocean, causing ocean warming and making Ocean Heat Content (OHC) a key indicator of climate change. However, accurately quantifying OHC remains difficult due to the evolving observing system, significant methodological differences, and varying data processing approaches. Despite its essential role in climate monitoring, there are currently no established guidelines for calculating the OHC indicator. In this presentation, we review the main challenges in estimating OHC and emphasize the urgent need for a coordinated international effort to establish the first set of recommendations for OHC assessment. A robust and consistent methodology is crucial for tracking past, present, and future climate change, and for addressing the pressing question of global warming acceleration. Our speaker Audrey Minière works at Ecole Normale Supérieure (ENS). "I am a postdoctoral researcher at the Laboratoire de Météorologie Dynamique (ENS, Paris), working on ocean warming. My research focuses on its spatial and temporal distribution and its estimation using a variety of observational data, including in situ measurements, satellite observations, and reanalyses. I work with Prof. Sabrina Speich and Dr. Karina von Schuckmann".

25 September 2025 | 10:00 - 10:45 CEST
Online

Audrey Minière (ENS)

**Estimating ocean warming: challenges
and recommendations for robust
assessment**

Danish Meteorological Institute

OCEAN:ICE

Funded by
the European Union

OCEAN ICE Climate coffee – October

Climate Coffee with Blanca Fernández-Álvarez on How Detection Frameworks Shape Our View of 2024's Mediterranean Marine Heatwaves

Oceans absorb most anthropogenic heat and a large share of carbon emissions, driving sea surface temperature (SST) increases and intensifying marine heatwaves (MHWs). Although rising MHW frequency is well documented, most studies rely on the standard fixed-baseline approach (Hobday et al., 2016), which uses a static climatology and is sensitive to long-term warming, thereby amplifying recent extremes and raising concerns about future MHW "saturation" (Rosselló et al., 2023). To address these issues, we compare three detection frameworks—fixed baseline (1982–2011), 20-year moving baseline (Rosselló et al., 2023), and a detrended method that removes the linear warming trend (Martínez et al., 2023)—across the Mediterranean Sea, a rapidly warming and ecologically vulnerable basin. Using SST data for 1982–2024,

all three methods identify 2024 as the peak MHW year of the past two decades, with fixed and moving baselines also registering the longest-lasting events. Regionally, the eastern Mediterranean, where warming is strongest, recorded the most MHW days in 2024, whereas the western basin experienced exceptionally intense events in 2022. Depending on the detection framework, estimated MHW exposure across the Mediterranean can vary by up to fourfold. Fixed baselines remain useful for assessing thermal stress relative to historical conditions, while moving and detrended methods better track anomalies in a changing climate. Aligning detection frameworks with research and policy goals is therefore crucial for reliable climate risk assessment and regional adaptation planning. The research of this talk has been published on Ocean Science

<https://os.copernicus.org/articles/21/1987/2025/>

30 October 2025 | 10:00 - 10:45 CET

Online

Blanca Fernández-Álvarez (IMEDEA-CSIC)

How Detection Frameworks Shape Our View of 2024's Mediterranean Marine Heatwaves

Danish Meteorological Institute

Funded by
the European Union

Climate Coffees

Since its relaunch the [Climate Coffee series](#) has been in full swing. If you've missed any of the recent ones, don't worry, you may catch up [here](#).

Climate Coffee

OCEAN ICE Deliverables and Milestones submitted

The OCEAN ICE community has been busy recently submitting various deliverables and milestones:

- D1.10 '[Local and remote processes' impacts on dense water formation'](#)
- D2.4 '[Observations of the ocean beneath Fimbul Ice Shelf'](#)
- D2.7 '[Ship and AUV observations near /within a warm ice-shelf cavity'](#)
- D1.6 '[Quality-controlled bottom pressure dataset to analyse for continental shelf waves: Contribution to WP1 OI'](#)
- D1.11 '[Observation-based multi-decadal time series of dense shelf water properties'](#)

The progress and results of OCEAN ICE are published in deliverables and milestone reports.

In order to keep up with the OCEAN ICE deliverables and milestones, visit our [website](#) and stay tuned on our social media channels.

Upcoming Events

Climate Coffee

We have an upcoming Climate Coffee in November and December, make sure you register for all of them through the link on [OCEAN ICE](#).

Climate Coffee with Natacha Legrix De La Salle on Surface and Subsurface Compound MHW and Biogeochemical Extremes Under Climate Change.

27 November 2025, 10:00 – 10:45 (CEST)

Climate Coffee

27 November 2025 | 10:00 - 10:45 CET
Online

Natacha Legrix De La Salle (Univ. Liverpool)

Surface and Subsurface Compound Marine Heatwave and Biogeochemical Extremes Under Climate Change

Danish Meteorological Institute

Funded by the European Union

Climate Coffee with Ioannis Prapas and Haralampos Gavriilidis on Manteo AI: Making Earth Observation Workflows More Intuitive

11 December 2025, 10:00 – 10:45 (CET)

Climate Coffee

11 December 2025 | 10:00 - 10:45 CET
Online

Ioannis Prapas and Haralampos Gavriilidis (Manteo)

Manteo AI: Making Earth Observation Workflows More Intuitive

Danish Meteorological Institute

Funded by the European Union

OCEAN ICE at Ocean Sciences Meeting

Members from OCEAN ICE will be presenting at the [Ocean Sciences Meeting in Glasgow, Scotland 2026](#). Please find the below talks during the meeting and look out for any future sessions/talks too:

David Chandler, Petra Langebroek, Heiko Goelzer, Michele Petrini and Morven Muilwijk.

Abstract ID: 2009920

Abstract Title: Global impacts of Greenland and Antarctic ice sheet freshwater fluxes in the Norwegian Earth System Model (NorESM)

Final Abstract Number: HE43A-09

Presentation Type: Oral

Session Number and Title: HE43A: Ice Sheet–Ocean Interactions: From Micro- to Climate-Scale II Oral

Session Date and Time: Thursday, 26 February 2026; 14:00 - 15:30 GMT

Presentation Time: 15:20 - 15:30 GMT

Location: SEC; Hall 3, Blue Horizon

Timothee Bourgeois, David Chandler, Michele Petrini, Elin Darelius, Petra Langebroek, Heiko Goelzer, and Jörg Schwinger.

Abstract ID: 2008310

Abstract Title: Committed Southern Ocean warming and implications for the Antarctic Ice Sheet following emission cessation

Presentation Type: Poster

Session Date and Time: Thursday, 26 February 2026; 16:00 - 18:00 GMT

Session Number and Title: HE44D: Variability, Circulation, and Ongoing Change in the Southern Ocean VI Poster

Location: SEC; Hall 4 (Poster Hall)

Zhetao Tan:

Changing Properties of South Atlantic Upper-Ocean Water Masses During the Past 45 Years' in session PS21A - Atlantic Ocean Connectivity Across Latitudes: Large-Scale Processes, Observations, Modeling, and Impacts, which are targeted to the OCEAN ICE topic.

Session Date and Time: Tuesday, 24 February 2026, 09:23 - 09:33

Location: Hall 1 (SEC)

Happening Soon

OCEAN ICE will be at these upcoming events. Will you also be there? Let us know!

- 3rd – 6th November 2025, [The Antarctica InSync Science Planning Workshop](#), Frascati, Italy
- 18th November 2025, Policy Briefing, Brussels, Belgium
- 9th – 12th February 2026, [Open Science Conference](#), New Zealand
- 22nd – 27th February 2025, [Ocean Sciences Meeting](#), Glasgow, Scotland
- 9th – 13th March 2026, [CMIP 2026 Meeting](#), Kyoto, Japan

Do you know of any exciting events that OCEAN ICE should be a part of? Shoot us a mail at oceanice.eu@gmail.com.

Are you following us on Social Media?

Stay up to date with OCEAN ICE on our following channels:

www.ocean-ice.eu

<https://www.linkedin.com/company/euoceanice/>

https://twitter.com/OCEANICE_EU

<https://fediscience.org/@OceanIceEU>

<https://www.facebook.com/OCEANICEEU/>

[OCEAN ICE \(@oceaniceeu.bsky.social\) — Bluesky](#)

Who is OCEAN ICE?

OCEAN ICE stands for Ocean-Cryosphere Exchanges in Antarctica: Impacts on Climate and the Earth System. OCEAN ICE is a Horizon Europe project, funded by the European Commission and UKRI. OCEAN ICE focus on understanding how the Antarctic ice sheet and the surrounding Southern Ocean influence our global climate and reduce the level of uncertainty around how much the Antarctic ice sheet will melt in the coming

centuries. OCEAN ICE considers the critical role of feedbacks between ocean circulation, ice sheet change and tipping points and the global climate. [Find out more](#)

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